

PVDF and PVDF-CTFE membranes for lithium-ion battery applications: A mini review

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Abstract. The battery production reached 1,490 GWh in 2024, with Li-ion batteries comprising 80%. This growing demand led to a tightening of conditions regarding enhanced battery safety and environmental impact. A key component influencing safety is the separator, which electrically insulates the electrodes while enabling the transport of lithium ions. Polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF) and its copolymer with chlorotrifluoroethylene (PVDF-CTFE) are promising alternatives to commercial separators. Their properties can be further improved using nanofillers to enhance mechanical strength, thermal resistance, electrochemical stability and ionic conductivity. This review emphasises that the selection of nanofillers can positively impact the safety-related properties of PVDF and contributes to the development of more efficient and durable energy storage solutions.

1. Introduction

In 2024, the global production capacity of battery energy storage systems exceeded 1 TWh. Lithium-ion (Li-ion) battery represents 80% of total electricity storage capacity and are used in wide range of applications, from grid-scale energy storage to portable electronic devices [1]. The growing demand for Li-ion batteries is bringing the attention on the economic, safety and ecological effects of individual components. One of these base components is the separator which functions as an insulator between the cathode and anode, restricting the free passage of electrons and preventing short-circuit of the battery while enabling the migration of Li-ions between the electrodes [2].

Today polyethylene and polypropylene (PP) are currently the most commonly used polymers for battery separator application. However, their use is limited by technological constraints relating to their porosity, wettability and thermal stability. These properties have a significant impact on the final safety of the battery, so it is necessary to find more suitable materials.

One of the most promising polymer materials is polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF), which is used in a variety of applications due to its unique properties. PVDF is a semicrystalline polymer with excellent mechanical, thermal and chemical durability [3]. Its properties can be further enhanced by using its copolymer polyvinylidene fluoride chlorotrifluoroethylene (PVDF-CTFE). This copolymer has high electromechanical response, high flexibility and greater chemical stability [4]. The halogen elements (significantly Cl) in the chain have flame-retarding function and C-Cl bond provides an active site for modification [5]. The properties of polymer materials can be significantly affected using nanofillers based on metal oxides or clay materials [6, 7].

2. Battery separator and demand on its properties

In a Li-ion battery the polymer membrane separator is exposed to chemically aggressive electrolyte environment, cyclic thermal stress and an applied electrical voltage. These operating conditions lead to the following requirements for the separator's properties to ensure safety, reliability and long battery life. General requirements for battery separator properties are summarised in Table 1 [8].

Table 1. Properties of PVDF nanocomposite materials [3].

Property	Requirement values
Mechanical stability	>98,0 MPa
Thickness	20-25 μm
Thermal stability	< 5% shrinkage in 60 min at 90°C
Stability in applied voltage	>4,3 V
Pore size	<1 μm
Pore size distribution	Uniform
Porosity	40-0 %
Ionic conductivity	>10 ⁻⁴ S/cm

The thickness of the separator significantly affects battery performance, impacting internal resistance and energy density. Thinner separators provide a shorter path for Li-ion transport, enhancing ion mobility. However, if the separator is too thin, it leads to reduced electrolyte uptake and lower mechanical strength, which compromises safety. For rechargeable batteries, a separator thickness of 25 μm or less is generally required. However, for batteries used in electric or hybrid vehicles, higher safety requirements mean that separators can be up to 40 μm thick to ensure stability at high voltages during the charging/discharging cycle [9, 10].

The porosity of separators determines its electrolyte absorption capacity. Low porosity (< 30 %) results in insufficient electrolyte uptake, which increases internal resistance and decreases ionic conductivity. Conversely, high porosity decreases mechanical strength and increases the risk

of malfunction. Additionally, separators with high porosity tend to shrink when exposed to heat [11].

The ionic conductivity and capacity of the battery also depend on the wettability of the electrolyte to the membrane. The separator must be able to absorb the electrolyte quickly and be able to retain it even during repeated charge/discharge cycles. The wetting rate depends on the properties of the separator such as porosity [12].

During operation, uneven pore size distribution will cause high local voltages, which will negatively affect battery performance by reducing electrode activity. While a low pore size reduced the separator resistance to metal ion migration is lower, large pores can cause indirect contact between the electrodes, increasing the risk of a short circuit [13].

The overall permeability of a polymer membrane separator is determined by its thickness, porosity, pore size and the distribution of these factors within the separator [10].

Mechanical stability, defined by tensile and puncture strength in the direction of Li-ion transport, is crucial. In a real battery, the separators and electrodes are under the mechanical tension. Deformation may result from external compression or internal pressure buildup caused by Li-ion dendrite growth. Separator shrinkage could result in electrode contact and electrical short circuiting. This is why the size of the separator must not change under applied voltage or cyclic temperature changes [14].

3. PVDF and PVDF-CTFE materials

A suitable alternative to polyolefin materials for use in battery separators is polyvinylidene fluoride (PVDF). PVDF is a semicrystalline polymer that is already widely used in energy applications due to its high chemical and mechanical stability, and stability in high temperatures (> 170 °C). A major advantage from production perspective is its good processability and self-standing properties [15]. PVDF exhibits three crystalline phases – α , β and γ (Fig. 1).

Figure 1. PVDF α , β and γ crystalline phases.

Poly(vinylidene fluoride-co-chlorotrifluoroethylene) (PVDF-CTFE) is a semi-crystalline polymer (Fig. 2) whose crystallinity is reduced by the presence of CTFE segments. This copolymer has a high electrochemical response and is highly flexible and elongated. It also has good mechanical properties and thermal stability, like other fluoropolymers as well as excellent chemical corrosion resistance [16]. The halogen elements (significantly Cl) in the chain have a flame-retarding function and the C-Cl bond provides an active site for modification [5].

Figure 2. PVDF-CTFE structure.

4. Preparation methods

A variety of techniques can be used to prepare polymer separators. Each method leads to the formation of a separator with different properties. The method chosen depends on the specific requirements of the final polymer membrane separator material.

The solvent casting method is widely used in the production of polymer nanocomposite membranes. In this process, a polymer and other components are dissolved in a solvent mixture to create a homogeneous solution, which is then cast onto a flat substrate. After solvent evaporation, the membrane can be peeled off as a free-standing film. This method can be used to prepare single or multilayered structures and can be modified by incorporating various nanofillers. However, uniform dispersion of nanoparticles remains problematic due to their tendency to agglomerate, resulting in poor dispersion [17].

Polymeric separators can be prepared using the phase inversion method. The two main types are non-solvent induced phase separation (NIPS) and thermally induced phase separation (TIPS). The NIPS method uses three components (polymer, solvent, and nonsolvent) and the separator is prepared by immersing the polymer solution in a non-solvent environment where the polymer solidifies. Membranes prepared by NIPS typically have a dense surface with an asymmetric morphology, suitable for reverse osmosis and nanofiltration processes. On the other hand, the TIPS method is typically employed with semi-crystalline polymers, and the principle is removing the solvents by their evaporation. TIPS method exhibits a highly porous and symmetric structure making them suitable for microfiltration and membrane contactor applications. TIPS is mainly used with semicrystalline polymers and produce highly porous materials. TIPS also offer better reproducibility and a lower defect rate but requires more energy [18].

Electrospinning is process used to prepare nanofibers with high porosity and interconnected pore structures. These separators enable high electrolyte uptake and unimpeded Li-ion transport. The morphology of electrospun membranes is influenced by solution properties like molecular weight and viscosity. Properties are affected even by processing parameter (voltage, flow rate) and environmental conditions (temperature, humidity). PVDF and its copolymer are commonly used for electrospun separators in Li-ion batteries due to their excellent compatibility and performance [19].

5. Multilayer material

Today single layer polymer separators are commonly modified using surface coating methods to enhance electrolyte wettability and thermal stability. Examples of these methods include dip coating, laminate, slot die, gravure coating, and curtain coating. The coated layer must preserve the porosity and structural integrity of the separator while improving electrolyte absorption [20].

One of the methods to prepare multilayer material is electrospinning. The nanofiber membranes have high porosity, which increases the electrolyte uptake capacity. Electrolyte uptake capacity is an important property for battery separators and directly correlate with amount of liquid electrolyte which can be absorb. In addition, nanofiber separator membranes have improved adhesion to the battery electrodes, which can help prevent the formation of gaps between the separators and electrodes during charge/discharge cycles, especially in large-format batteries. Even a small failure of the interfacial adhesion between the separator and the electrode can increase battery impedance causing uneven current distribution and leading to the formation of lithium dendrite growth. Many of these nanofiber membranes can adhere to a battery electrode by using polymers such as PVDF and PVDF co-polymers [20].

6. Nanofillers

Metal oxides, clay materials, and organic components are used as nanofillers for polymer nanocomposite separators. Metal oxides specifically influence the ionic conductivity of the separators [21], wettability to the electrolyte, reduce the shape shrinkage due to high temperature, thermal stability, limit the growth of Li-ion dendrites [22], improve electrochemical properties, stability at high applied voltage [23], mechanical resistance and increase porosity [24]. Due to their availability and cost-effectiveness can be used in large-scale production.

Clay materials specifically vermiculite particles are applied as a substrate for the targeted growth of metal oxide nanoparticles. Its incorporation into polymer matrix increasing thermal stability and mechanical strength. High strength prevents the penetration of Li-ion dendrites into the membrane and at the same time allows the passage of Li-ion through the interlayer space. The presence of vermiculite particles in the polymer matrix also improves its wettability [25].

The effect of various nanofillers on PVDF polymer materials is investigated on zinc oxide nanoparticles (ZnO), vermiculite (V), chlorhexidine (CH) and their combinations as nanofillers. Effect of 3 wt.% of various nanofillers on specific properties are shown in Table 2. The ζ - potential demonstrate the stability of the separator in specific medium. The biggest difference was shown by nanofillers combination of vermiculite and chlorhexidine and in combination of zinc oxide, vermiculite and chlorhexidine. This correspond the chlorhexidine is the one who is responsible for the decrease of ζ - potential. In difference the water contact angle increases by presence of all nanofillers also increase the crystallinity of PVDF (only PVDF_V decrease) and thickness of polymer separator. Thermal stability weren't highly effected by use of nanofillers and the values were moving around 171 °C. The sample PVDF_V was only one which represented the increase of Friction coefficient and reach value >1. The presence of rest of nanofillers resulted in slight decrease in Friction coefficient [6,7].

Table 2. Properties of the PVDF nanocomposite material [6,7].

Samples	ζ - potential [mV]	Water contact angle [°]	Crystallinity [%]	Thickness [μm]	Thermal stability [°C]	Friction coefficient [-]
PVDF	-63,5	43	41,2	42	169,3	0,91
PVDF_V	-60,1	64	39,3	47	173,9	1,07
PVDF_V_CH	-36,1	67	46,1	62	169,7	0,87
PVDF_ZnO	-58,8	69	51,7	56	171,6	0,86
PVDF_ZnO/V	-53,7	64	51,7	62	171,5	0,83
PVDF_ZnO/V_CH	-16,6	58	70,2	66	171,2	0,79

The use of various inorganic fillers has a significant effect on PVDF-CTFE, as demonstrated in the study [26]. In this case, the fillers used were at a concentration of 5 wt.%. The results show that the pore size increase as the valence of the metal cation increases. This corresponds with the results in Table 3, which show that the porosity and pore size of the membranes increase with the valence of the metal cation. The highest porosity and pore size are found with the trivalent salt FeCl_3 , and the lowest values are found with the monovalent salt NaNO_3 .

Table 3. The effect of inorganic fillers on the properties of PVDF-CTFE [26].

Filler	Mean pore size [μm]	Water contact angle [°]	Porosity [%]
LiCl	0,113	97,5	70,9
MgCl_2	0,112	93,2	72,3
FeCl_3	0,138	82,7	74,4
NaNO_2	0,088	94,6	64,2
H_3PO_4	0,175	99,2	66,7

7. Conclusion

The review summarised the critical requirements for the properties of polymer membrane separators used in Li-ion batteries, focusing on PVDF and PVDF-CTFE polymers. The performance of the separator is greatly influenced by its thickness, porosity, pore size and distribution, and the mechanical, thermal and chemical properties of the material used. These properties directly affect electrolyte uptake, Li-ion transport, and the safety of the final battery.

PVDF and its copolymers exhibit the required properties for battery applications due to their thermal, chemical and mechanical stability. They can be prepared using various methods to achieve the required properties for a specific application.

The use of nanofillers such as metal oxides, clay minerals and organic compounds has been demonstrated to significantly improve membrane performance by enhancing ionic conductivity, wettability and mechanical strength. Nanofillers based on zinc oxide nanoparticles grown on vermiculite show promising effects on the polymer matrix.

The development of PVDF-based nanocomposite separators, which combine advances in preparation methods and modification techniques with the use of nanofillers, represents a possible strategy for meeting the increasing demand for materials used in batteries.

Data availability

The data that support the findings of this study are openly available in repository ZENODO at <https://zenodo.org/records/15743322>.

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